

ANNUAL REPORT

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DIRECTOR'S INTRODUCTION

Chris Speed
Director Creative Informatics

Creative Informatics is part of the Creative Industries Clusters Programme; a UK wide initiative designed to drive innovation, growth, and sustainability in the creative industries, through a first-of-its-kind research and development investment of £80m by the UK government.

With a focus on Edinburgh and South East Scotland, Creative Informatics is working to drive growth and sustainability in this region's world class creative industries by supporting creative individuals and organisations to do inspiring things with data. The programme is led by the University of Edinburgh and is delivered in partnership with Edinburgh Napier University, CodeBase and Creative Edinburgh. This report provides a snapshot of what the Creative Informatics partnership has achieved over the last two years, as we reach the midway point of our funding period.

Despite the unprecedented challenges of 2020, brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic, I am pleased to say that Creative Informatics has provided significant support, insight and energy to Edinburgh and South East Scotland's creative community. To date we have invested £1.86m in the creative industries through our funding and development programmes.

Full credit should go to our delivery and research teams for driving Creative Informatics forward during this difficult time and extending our planned community engagement, despite all of our meetings, workshops and events moving online.

Our events programme, which includes CI Labs, CI Studios and our annual CI Innovation Showcase, has reached over 1,700 participants and developed the presence of Creative Informatics across national and international networks. In response to Covid-19, we developed FridayForum, a new series of events delivered in partnership with Visual Arts Scotland during the spring/summer 2020 lockdown, to support creatives facing a loss of income due to the pandemic.

»For every £1 R&D investment in cluster companies around £1.74 is generated in additional investment, grants and in-kind value.«

The small investments that Creative Informatics made during its first year have started to return larger financing from external investors. There has been £1.1m investment across three companies, and we have observed a further total of £0.75m in funding awards across 14 companies. For every £1 R&D investment in cluster companies around £1.74 is generated in investment, grants and in-kind value. To date we have supported 18 new spin outs, start-ups, and significant business pivots; 46 new or safeguarded jobs; 66 Minimum Viable Products and 29 new products, services and experiences.

In addition to supporting R&D within the cluster, Creative Informatics has also been doing its own research, with highlights including the mapping of freelancers in the region ↪, publishing our own Data Management Plan ↪, and developing a Creative Informatics guide for running online events ↪.

Our research team have also contributed to the development of work responding to Covid-19 for the Fruitmarket Gallery ↗ and Talbot Rice Gallery ↗, and curated Small Research Grant calls for Early Career Researchers ↗, growing the Creative Informatics research community at the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University.

The achievements of our programme have been recognised in the publication of the Developing Data-Driven Innovation in Creative Industries report ↗, led by Caroline Parkinson, which recommends an extension to the CI programme to help Edinburgh and South East Scotland's creative sectors develop through better use of data-driven innovation and technology. Warmly received across the creative industries, the report is informing policy within Scottish Government toward future investment.

Please read on to find out more about the work we have been doing and the impact we are having on Edinburgh's creative ecosystem. I hope you will continue to engage with our programme and get involved in the Creative Informatics community where you can.

Chris Speed
 DIRECTOR
 Creative Informatics
 ↗ c.speed@ed.ac.uk

WHAT WE DO

Creative Informatics is nurturing local talent in Edinburgh and SE Scotland through five key funding and development programmes that support individuals and organisations working in the creative industries to develop new products, businesses and experiences using data and data-driven technologies.

↳ creativeinformatics.com

CREATIVE INFORMATICS IMPACT

	£2.32m	FUNDING COMMITTED to Edinburgh and SE Scotland's creative industries
	200	PARTICIPANTS RECEIVED FUNDING through all Creative Informatics strands
	2235	ENGAGEMENTS with creative enterprises
	62	MINIMUM VIABLE PRODUCTS developed by programme participants
	6	NEW BUSINESSES formed by CI participants to date
	£1.85m	EXTERNAL INVESTMENT RAISED by CI companies to date
	£1.4m	IN-KIND SUPPORT for Creative Informatics projects

Figures correct at 31.05.2021

OUR FUNDING PROGRAMMES

Creatives can apply to any of our individual funding programmes, or choose to develop their data-driven proposition as part of journey through multiple Creative Informatics funding strands.

CHALLENGE PROJECTS

Challenge Projects offer an opportunity for creative and cultural organisations to bring forward challenges relating to their work that require innovative, data-driven solutions. Challenge Holders can come with unformed or semi-formed challenges that can be co-designed with the Creative Informatics team. Individuals or SMEs with the skills to answer a Challenge Project can apply for funding of up to £20k as a Challenge Respondent.

Challenge Holders include National Theatre of Scotland, Historic Environment Scotland, Scottish Opera, Edinburgh International Festival, and the Edinburgh Festival Fringe Society.

→ Applications open twice a year in April and October. See case study p. 32

RESIDENT ENTREPRENEURS

Individuals and small teams that would like to develop a new product or service using data or data-driven technology can apply to be a Resident Entrepreneur. Successful applicants receive £12k of funding, plus mentoring and support from the CI team.

→ Applications open twice a year in April and October. See case study p. 29

CREATIVE BRIDGE

Creative Bridge is a fully-funded course for creatives of all backgrounds, delivered by CodeBase. Whether you have a business idea, or you'd just like to know more about startup thinking, Creative Bridge aims to demystify the tech world and its jargon, sharing the building blocks of digital product development over 10 weeks.

→ Applications open up to three times a year. See case study p. 26

CONNECTED INNOVATORS

Connected Innovators supports emerging leaders from within the creative industries to undertake research and development that will enable them to advance their own careers and/or business, as well as benefiting the wider creative community. Successful applicants receive £10k of funding to develop a specific area of their creative practice or business using data or data-driven technology.

→ Applications for Connected Innovators open twice a year. See case study p. 35

CREATIVE HORIZON PROJECTS

Creative Horizon Projects are aimed at interdisciplinary teams of academic and industry partners. Up to £25k of funding is available for projects that explore the potential of emerging technologies to create new technical and business opportunities for the creative industries in Edinburgh and South East Scotland.

→ See case study p. 38

Find out more about projects we've funded on p. 21–36 and via our newly launched community page over on the CI website.

↳ creativeinformatics.com/community

WHO WE SUPPORT

Our funding and development opportunities are open to anyone working in or with the creative industries in Edinburgh and South East Scotland. We work with individuals and organisations across all creative sectors and this is reflected in the diverse range of applications we receive and projects we have supported to date.

89 DESIGN (PRODUCT, GRAPHIC, FASHION)

87 MUSIC, PERFORMING AND VISUAL ARTS

83 IT, SOFTWARE AND COMP SERVICES

54 FILM, TV, VIDEO, RADIO AND PHOTO

31 ADVERTISING AND MARKETING

29 OTHER

PROGRAMME STATISTICS

PROGRAMME	PARTICIPANTS	APPLICANTS
CHALLENGE HOLDERS	17	39
CHALLENGE RESPONDENTS	11	47
CREATIVE BRIDGE	148	226
RESIDENT ENTREPRENEURS	36	132
CONNECTED INNOVATORS	13	92

24 PUBLISHING

22 MUSEUMS, GALLERIES AND LIBRARIES

16 CRAFTS

11 ARCHITECTURE

Funded participants span creative sectors with some identifying across more than one sector. They are particularly drawn from Design; Music, Performance and Visual Arts; and IT, software & computing services.

UNIQUE BUSINESS INVESTMENT

Companies supported by Creative Informatics have already secured over £1.85m in additional funding, ranging from small grant awards (£5k+) to Innovate UK R&D funding (Insurgent Studios: £650k, Stageport: £300k).

DELIC / SUPERRATIONAL

Delic, a new platform developed by start-up SuperRational Ltd with funding from our Resident Entrepreneur strand, enables highly innovative registering and tracing of music contributions and rights, so that musicians can ensure they are properly credited for their work.

Ed Stack, Creative Director of SuperRational Ltd and Founder of Delic, took part in the pilot run of Creative Bridge and found that the course helped him to develop the platform's business proposition. As a direct result of his participation in Creative Bridge, Ed entered into talks with investors and subsequently secured £375k of investment, leading to five full time and six part time/contracted jobs to support further development of Delic.

→ delic.network

TOUHLAB

Resident Entrepreneurs Touchlab are an electronic skin and robotics company integrating sensing technology into any surface. They have been selected as semi-finalists in the global ANA Avatar XPrize competition to build a tele-operated avatar system that will transport a human's sense, actions, and presence to a remote location in real time. Touchlab used their RE funding to work with VR/AR experts to develop the human user experience for controlling their avatar.

In October 2020 they won the £100k Higgs EDGE prize at the Scottish Edge Awards for their ground-breaking work and have since secured a substantial joint investment from Techstart Ventures Scotland, Creator Fund and a number of private investors to continue developing electronic skin that will give robots a human-like sense of touch.

→ touchlab.io

PICOJAR

Picojar uses a combination of Optical Character Recognition, Natural Language Processing and computer vision in an AI-powered workflow to enable innovative visual notetaking. Founder Siwei Kang was selected as a Resident Entrepreneur (RE) in February 2020, using the funding to progress her proof of concept app.

In June 2020, Picojar raised \$185k of investment to support further development of the product towards market.

Picojar's journey demonstrates the benefits of Creative Informatics as part of Edinburgh's startup ecosystem. Our RE programme offers flexible funding, enabling founders to focus on taking their product or service to the next stage, and complimenting other sources of support and funding often aimed at earlier or later stage SMEs.

→ picojar.com

ENGAGING WITH THE COMMUNITY

A key challenge in bringing Creative Informatics to life was finding ways to engage the creative community in Edinburgh and South East Scotland with the aims and objectives of our programme.

L. E11 Studio in Edinburgh Napier University

SUPPORTING THE WIDER CREATIVE COMMUNITY

Creative Informatics is increasingly recognised as a key broker for connecting creative and cultural organisations with creative technologists and innovators across the region, facilitating collaborations across creative sub sectors and between large and small organisations.

Beyond our funding and development strands, we have supported a number of projects and programmes in the region’s wider creative community.

RUNWAYS

Using data to develop products, services and experiences is a new concept for many creative practitioners, so establishing effective runways to introduce Creative Informatics to the region’s creative community has been key to the programme’s success.

- DISCOVERY WORKSHOPS**
Informal sessions where potential applicants can shape their application ideas with support from our research team.
- CONNECTED INNOVATOR DROP INS**
The Creative Edinburgh team run regular drop in sessions for potential applicants who would like support or advice on submitting their application.
- CREATIVE BRIDGE DROP INS**
Drop in sessions with the Creative Bridge team at CodeBase, where potential applicants can find out more and raise any questions they have about the application process.
- ONE-TO-ONES**
One to one sessions are offered for all our funding and development strands for applicants that have particular questions about their application or require additional support.
- CHALLENGE HOLDER Q&As**
An opportunity for Challenge Holders to introduce their projects and answer questions from individuals and organisations interested in submitting a Challenge Respondent application.
- FEEDBACK**
We provide extensive feedback to applicants for all our funding strands, enabling them to develop their approach and improve future applications, building the confidence of creatives working with data across the region.

L. Creative Edinburgh Awards 2019

BUILDING NEW PARTNERSHIPS

We work closely with Creative Edinburgh, CodeBase, and Edinburgh Napier University to tap into different networks in the region’s creative ecosystem. We are always open to new collaborations and have run events and workshops with a host of creative and tech focussed organisations including:

- Visual Arts Scotland**
- Creative Edinburgh Awards**
- Ada Scotland Festival**
- Creative & Cultural Careers Festival (UoE)**
- Tinderbox Collective**

RAISE YOUR GAME

A new workshop series designed to develop digital and data skills in the creative industries.

[L bit.ly/CI-RYG](https://bit.ly/CI-RYG)

L Illustrations by Erik Ravaglia

Raise Your Game (RYG) is a digital skills programme for creatives, established by CREATIVE EDINBURGH in partnership with Creative Informatics and supported by Edinburgh Futures Institute. RYG was developed in response to a gap in skills, knowledge and confidence around data and digital within the creative industries.

The programme is targeted at early stage creative freelancers, whether embarking on or pivoting their career in the creative industries and is delivered across eight workshops, supported by additional resources and an online space for connection and self-reflection. RYG sessions focus on digital skills, data and future-proof working models, as well as the fundamentals of goal setting and business management for creatives.

»Raise Your Game is a great 'starter pack' for those looking to start or expand their business or themselves with a digital focus but broad brush support, knowledge and encouragement. It encompasses some more traditional areas of focus and some great alternatives to stimulate sustainable and lateral thinking.«

Attendee RYG pilot

EVENTS

We run a year-round programme of free events to showcase innovation across the creative industries and provide opportunities for individuals to find out more about working with data and emerging technologies.

[L creativeinformatics.com/events](https://creativeinformatics.com/events)

	17	CI LABS presented in partnership with creative and cultural venues in Edinburgh
	12	CI STUDIOS offering opportunities to explore emerging technologies
	3	PARTNERSHIP FORUMS for the creative community to share their feedback on Creative Informatics
	1	CI INNOVATION SHOWCASE in 2020 with 300 attendees

PARTNERSHIP FORUM

Our Partnership Forum events are open to anyone working in or with the creative industries in Edinburgh and South East Scotland. These events play a crucial role in shaping our activity, providing an opportunity for the creative community to feedback on their experience and understanding of Creative Informatics, and helping us to identify areas where we are delivering well or could be doing better.

CI LABS

CI Labs feature talks, demonstrations and/or live performances from creative practitioners and academics who are working with data and data-driven technologies, as well as providing opportunities to network and hear about upcoming and current funding calls.

Due to Covid-19 our CI Labs programme has switched to a mix of online and hybrid events, streaming live from venues in Edinburgh including Leith Theatre, Riddle's Court and CodeBase, to an international online audience.

Our CI Lab speakers have included:

- Rachel McLean
- Dan Hett
- Chagall

L CI LAB#16 (hybrid event) in the Smart Venue Effenaar (Eindhoven, NL) with music producer and songwriter Chagall and 4DR Studios.

CI STUDIOS

CI Studios provide opportunities for creative practitioners of all disciplines to explore new approaches to working and experimenting with data and emerging technologies in an informal environment. Our team at Edinburgh Napier University lead on the CI Studios programme and have established E11 Studio as a dedicated space for workshops at their Merchiston Campus.

Topics for CI Studios have included:

- Exploring Livestreaming Economies
- Getting Creative with Climate Data (Hybrid E11 Studio & Zoom event)
- Introducing BBC Makerbox

L CI STUDIO #2 Scanning 3D-Artifacts with John Morrison

L FABI FABI

FRIDAY FORUM

Responding to the Covid-19 crisis with Visual Arts Scotland.

L creativeinformatics.com/fridayforum

SUPPORTING CREATIVES THROUGH LOCKDOWN

Friday Forum was a series of 12 online sharing events for creatives of all disciplines, delivered by the Creative Informatics team in partnership with Visual Arts Scotland. The series was established in April 2020 to support individuals in the creative industries facing a loss of income due to Covid-19, loss of opportunities to showcase their work, and loss of networking and connection spaces.

Each Friday Forum featured four paid contributors who showcased snippets of their work, gave virtual tours around their studio spaces, or provided insights into their creative practice or career. The series ran until July 2020 and created a new supportive space to share and celebrate creative work and bring together diverse practices, including technical and data-driven work alongside more traditional fine arts and crafts.

»Thanks to you I found the courage to launch a project that deserves to be known. I've met and known a lot of interesting people in a world that sometimes is not so easy to see and to be in contact with.«

Anna Francesca Schiraldi, Speaker at FF #12

RESEARCH

Creative Informatics researchers at the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University are actively engaged in a wide range of projects exploring the current and evolving landscapes of the creative industries in and around Edinburgh and SE Scotland.

↳ creativeinformatics.com/research

EDINBURGH FESTIVAL FRINGE SOCIETY

Ongoing strategic research partnerships with the creative industries

Creative Informatics has established strategic relationships with key players in the creative industries in Edinburgh and beyond, including the Edinburgh Festival Fringe Society, custodians of the largest arts festival in the world. The Fringe Society participated in the pilot run of our Challenge Projects, trialling an innovative 'discovery workshop' model to assist with their challenge ideation process.

This collaborative process paved the way for their Challenge Project with inChat, and several other Creative Informatics research projects exploring the Fringe ecosystem, including *Cost of the Fringe* in 2019, *Emerging Models of the Edinburgh Fringe: Supporting Fringe Performers in Online Spaces* and *Cataloguing Emerging Online Economies for Festivals and the Performing Arts* in 2020.

IMPROVBOT

The world's first AI-generated events programme for a virtual arts festival

ImprovBot.AI was an experimental AI bot trained on eight years of Edinburgh Festival Fringe programmes, to create the World's first AI generated arts festival programme. The bot was developed by Creative Informatics Co-Director Professor Melissa Terras, in collaboration with creative technologist Gavin Inglis and independent scholar and artist Rudolf Ammann. The team used *archer*, the UK National Supercomputer based at the Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre to engage with the extensive Fringe programme data.

The bot received a 4 star review from *The Stage* and shared content throughout August 2020 via Twitter, with some of the fictional shows generated turned into short YouTube sketches by the University of Edinburgh's student comedy troupe *The Improverts*.

CIVIC DIGITS THEATRE COMPANY AND THE BIG DATA SHOW

Collaborative R&D into New Modalities of Experience

Civic Digits approached Creative Informatics in late 2019 to collaborate on a series of workshops as part of a tour of *The Big Data Show*, an immersive show for schools exploring cyber resilience and digital citizenship. CI researchers worked with Civic Digits to develop a 'data physicalisation' workshop that enables participants to build their own motorised emoji, using *VizBlocks* software and hardware developed at the Institute for Design Informatics (University of Edinburgh).

The tour was put on hold due to Covid-19, however, Civic Digits created a successful digital version of *The Big Data Show* and are now working with CI to package the *VizBlock* workshops so they can be shared with schools as an accompaniment to the online show.

DIRECTORATE

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CREATIVE BRIDGE

CREATIVE BRIDGE PROGRAMME LEAD
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HEAD OF BRIDGE PROGRAMMES
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CREATIVE BRIDGE LEAD
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JANINE MATHESON

CONNECTED INNOVATORS

EVENT PRODUCER
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PROGRAMME MANAGER
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SUSAN LEHELDT
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PIP THORNTON

RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEER
EVAN MORGAN

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Partner: Codebase

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Partner: Creative Edinburgh

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Insurgent Studios

36 FUTURE PLANS

Creative Bridge is a fully funded, 10-week course for creatives with early stage business ideas, who want to learn about startup thinking, innovation and digital product development.

→ Applications open three times a year.

»Creative Bridge was exactly what I needed to take the next step in my career, providing me with a step by step guide to setting up a business, in a learning environment that was super nurturing and encouraging.«

→ Elena Höge | Yaldi Games

148

PARTICIPANTS
to date

53

MINIMUM VIABLE PRODUCTS
developed by participants

4

NEW BUSINESSES
established by participants

ELENA HÖGE

FROM CREATIVE IDEA TO AWARD-WINNING STARTUP

Elena Höge founded Yaldi Games in January 2020, one month after completing Creative Bridge. The programme helped Elena in developing her early stage idea into a new creative business, learning how to understand her market, create lean canvases, and identify the right business model for her product.

Elena was featured at the Creative Informatics Innovation Showcase in June 2020, where she shared her Creative Bridge experience and talked about future plans for Yaldi Games. In September 2020 Yaldi Games' first release *Wholesome* won top prize in the Creative Challenge category at the Converge Awards, receiving £20k in cash and £21k in in-kind business support. The company continues to go from strength to strength and recently won a Young Innovator Award 2020/21 from Innovate UK and the Prince's Trust.

↳ yaldigames.com

CODEBASE

Creative Bridge is delivered by our partner CodeBase

↳ thisiscodebase.com

CodeBase, the UK's largest technology incubator, plays an instrumental role in the Creative Informatics partnership, leading on the development and delivery of Creative Bridge and promoting the wider Creative Informatics programme to their thriving network of entrepreneurs and startups.

They have been heavily involved in post-Covid-19 recovery policy discussions for both the Scottish and UK Government, receiving substantial recognition in the 'Scottish Technology Ecosystem Review', and participating in the Economic Recovery Task Force and DCMS Digital Strategy Workshops.

Plans are currently underway to develop a postgraduate Creative Bridge programme for the University of Edinburgh, drawing on the expertise of the CodeBase team to offer a new postgraduate course at the Edinburgh Futures Institute.

 AWARD WINNER Creative Bridge won The City Award at the Creative Edinburgh Awards 2020

 PODCAST The Creative Bridge podcast features conversations with some of the super talented individuals that have taken part in the course.
↳ thisiscodebase.com/creative-bridge

RESIDENT ENTREPRENEURS

Resident Entrepreneurs receive £12k of funding, plus mentoring and support to develop a new creative product or service using data or data-driven technologies.

→ Applications open twice a year

»The programme has provided me with the time and space to develop and deliver work that before I could only outline or describe. The mentoring element has also proved invaluable by helping me to distill and clarify my practice, helping me to successfully compete for commissions.«

→ Rebecca Kaye | Ploterre

 36 RE PROJECTS funded to date

 3 ADDITIONAL FUNDING secured as Challenge Respondents

 £1.47m FURTHER INVESTMENT secured by RE participants (incl. Creative Bridge alumni)

MARTIN DISLEY

SUPPORTING COLLABORATIONS WITHIN THE START-UP ECOSYSTEM

Martin Disley was hosted by the National Library of Scotland (NLS) for the duration of his Resident Entrepreneur project, using cutting edge generative machine learning technologies (GANs) to create new fictional maps based on the Library's vast digitised collections.

The work produced by Martin helped raise his profile as an artist and earned him a nomination for the John Byrne Award in Spring 2020. He has since pivoted his practice towards »oblique technology research«, exploring cutting edge computational creative approaches. Through his involvement in Creative Informatics, Martin also secured work with fellow Resident Entrepreneurs Delic Network, providing technology research and software development assistance. He was one of seven artists selected to take part in the Creative Informatics supported Zoom Obscura project, which launched in April 2021.

↳ martindisley.co.uk

REBECCA KAYE

PIVOTING DURING COVID-19 THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW DATA SKILLS

During her Resident Entrepreneur (RE) project Rebecca Kaye had planned to undertake research and development that would enable her to reduce costs, broaden her client range, and experiment with new data-driven work.

However, due to Covid-19, hiring a developer to work with proved challenging, so Rebecca decided to change course and spend time learning the technical skills required to realise her ambitions, which ultimately gave her greater economic and creative control over her project. She re-branded her company as PLOTTERRE and, with support from her CI mentor, shifted the focus of her business to communicating environmental data in engaging and thoughtfully produced creative visualisations. In November 2020, Rebecca secured funding from Creative Scotland to develop her work further.

↳ ploterre.com

CHALLENGE PROJECTS

Challenge Projects offer an opportunity for creative organisations to bring forward challenges relating to their work that require innovative, data-driven solutions.

→ Applications open twice a year

Challenge Holders can come with unformed or semi-formed challenges that can be co-designed with the Creative Informatics team. Up to £20k is available to support Challenge Respondents (individuals or SMEs) that suggest research and development proposals to answer a Challenge Project.

Challenge Holders include

- National Theatre of Scotland
- Historic Environment Scotland
- Scottish Opera
- Edinburgh International Festival
- Edinburgh Festival Fringe Society
- Pianodrome

17

CHALLENGE PROJECTS

Since launch in MARCH 2019

11

CHALLENGE RESPONDENTS

Selected to date

BRIGHT WHITE & EDINBURGH UNESCO CITY OF LITERATURE

Edinburgh UNESCO City of Literature Trust's Challenge Project was to develop an immersive visitor experience for their Literature House, currently under development at the historic John Knox House site in Edinburgh. Interpretive design and build consultancy Bright White, working in partnership with Offbeat Studios in Edinburgh, were selected to respond to this broad creative brief.

The Bright White team have created an innovative new platform and workflows enabling incredible spatial audio experiences that will be trialled in the Literature House in 2021. As a direct result of undertaking testing during lockdown, Bright White are also exploring a domestic version of this product that could offer highly immersive sound experiences to users at home.

L brightwhiteltd.co.uk

L offbeat.co.uk

L cityofliterature.com

VIAPONTICA & THE LIST

The List, the UK's leading live events data business, set a Challenge Project which required a Challenge Respondent to develop an automated technological solution to resize collections of images in a range of formats and across a range of media. Previously, their image cropping had been carried out through a combination of existing automation tools and manual checking and correction which was time-consuming and expensive.

Boutique machine learning consultancy Viapontica were successful and delivered an AI software for fully automated, aesthetic and text-aware image cropping. The List have undertaken significant testing of this product and see significant value in adopting it as part of their day-to-day business. The two partners are now considering how best to take the idea forward, both within existing systems at The List, and as a product for the wider market.

↳ viapontica.ai

CONNECTED INNOVATORS

Connected Innovators receive up to £10k of funding and support to develop their creative practice or business using data or data-driven technology.

→ Applications open twice a year

»Connected Innovators has allowed me to evolve my interdisciplinary practice through mainly developing my knowledge of sound and light design with data-driven tech, but also allowing me to develop new ideas for participatory artworks and finding ways to make my business more sustainable. I cannot underestimate how transformative it has been to receive this support.«

→ Sarah Calmus

92

CONNECTED INNOVATOR APPLICANTS to date

13

PROJECTS FUNDED in first two calls

BRIAN BAGLOW

SCOTTISH GAMES NETWORK

Brian Baglow is a writer, games designer, and founder of the Scottish Games Network, the industry body for the video games sector in Scotland. Scottish Games Network supports Scotland's gaming industry to connect to other sectors and regions, promoting interactive media as a transformative technology.

Through his Connected Innovators project, Brian is undertaking data led research into Scotland's games sector, mapping out the companies and individuals that make up the country's games industry and identifying opportunities for further funding, development and growth. His research is already providing valuable insight into the size, scope and most common practices of Scotland's diverse gaming community.

↳ scottishgames.net

CREATIVE EDINBURGH

Connected Innovators is delivered by our partners Creative Edinburgh
↳ creative-edinburgh.com

Connected Innovators is delivered by Creative Edinburgh, who provide support for individuals and organisations working in the city's creative industries, offering career development opportunities and advocacy, as well as running regular events and workshops.

Creative Edinburgh are a crucial part of the Creative Informatics partnership, ensuring that our funding and development opportunities reach their creative network of 5,000 members, and providing creative industries mentors for our Resident Entrepreneurs and Connected Innovators.

As well as developing their own creative practice or business, Connected Innovators should also be able to demonstrate how their work will benefit the wider creative community and what the social impact of their work will be.

SKILLS DEVELOPMENT

RAISE YOUR GAME

Delivering digital skills and confidence building to creatives. See p. 14

160

RAISE YOUR GAME Attendees

With 105 unique attendees

CREATIVE HORIZON PROJECTS

Creative Horizon Projects should be high risk/high gain in nature, bringing academics and industry together with the aim of breaking new ground and considering how technology could benefit the creative industries in the future.

↳ creativeinformatics.org/creative-horizon-projects

»Our approach allowed us to present a detailed 3D visualisation of delicate, physical assets from Edinburgh College of Art’s wide range of student projects through the medium of VR & AR head mounted display devices. We are delighted to have been able to help to preserve historical assets and make them available for students and researchers in the future.«

→ Craig Hunter | INSURGENT STUDIOS Ltd

£25K

FUNDING AWARDED

to work with cutting-edge technologies

CONFERENCE

29–30TH April 2021

ANIMATION RESEARCH NETWORK SCOTLAND
Bringing Legacy to Life Stop Motion Conference

INSURGENT STUDIOS LTD & ECA ANIMATION

Edinburgh College of Art (ECA) Animation was keen to mark its 30th Anniversary in 2020 by celebrating and reimagining its student film archive and finding a way to preserve this unique but increasingly fragile material.

Dr Nichola Dobson and Jared Taylor at ECA worked with creative and digital agency Insurgent Studios Limited (ISL) to develop new processes to capture and digitise legacy student films, including animation footage and original puppets along with newly replicated digital 3D set models.

The Insurgent Studios team developed these new digital assets in to both VR and AR experiences that replicate the experience of being in an animation studio, integrating the fragile physical archive material as accessible, movable, interactive digital objects that enable a deeper connection with previous animators’ processes and a novel pedagogical method for both on-campus and distance education.

↳ insurgentstudios.com

↳ eca.ed.ac.uk

FUTURE PLANS

We are now developing national and international partnerships to enable us to scale our methods, and to build opportunities for the creative industries organisations in our network to thrive and grow.

Creative Informatics directly supports two critical forms of innovation: Continuous Innovation, the adoption and use of data-driven technologies to enhance established businesses and organisations; and Disruptive Innovation, fuelling start-up cultures that allow new businesses to emerge that use data-driven technology to introduce new experiences, business models and services for the creative industries.

With a wide 'funnel' that onboards members across all sub-sectors through events, skills, collaboration models and value creation, Creative Informatics has become an exemplar in the Edinburgh and South East Scotland City Region.

In addition, Creative Informatics will continue to deliver support through our four primary funding streams in the year ahead investing in a further: **10 Challenge Projects**; **18 Resident Entrepreneurs**; **8 Connected Innovators**; **2 Creative Horizon projects**.

We will continue to deliver compelling live events through our Labs, Studios and annual Innovation Showcase; grow our suite of skills programmes aimed at students, entrepreneurs and established businesses/organisations; and extend our involvement in UK and EU funding initiatives through the co-creation of R&D challenges with industry.

Find out more and get involved at

creativeinformatics.com

Creative Informatics is a major research and development programme for Edinburgh & SE Scotland's creative industries, providing funding opportunities for individuals and organisations to develop ground-breaking products, businesses and experiences using data and data-driven technologies.

↳ creativeinformatics.org

CONTACT

If you have any questions get in touch at

↳ creativeinformatics@ed.ac.uk

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↳ creativeindustriesclusters.com

Creative Industries X Clusters
Programme

The programme is part of the City Region Deal Data Driven Innovation initiative.

We are nurturing talent through five key funding programmes and regular events that support Edinburgh's creative industries to do inspiring things with data.

↳ creativeinformatics.org

